

Acoustical studies of some derivatives of ethylbenzene-1,3-diol in dimethylformamide solution at 308.15 K^ψ

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Manuscript received 14 October 2003, accepted 5 February 2004

The derivatives of ethylbenzene-1,3-diol have been synthesized and characterized by TLC, IR and NMR spectral data. Various parameters, such as specific impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (K_s), intermolecular free length (L_f), Rao's molar sound function (R_m), molar compressibility (W), Van der Waals constant (b), free volume (V_f), solvation number (S_n) etc., have been calculated from the experimental data of ultrasonic velocity and density at 308.15 K. The results are interpreted in terms of molecular interactions occurring in the solutions.

A literature survey shows that there has been an increased interest in thermodynamic and transport properties of liquid solutions and in liquid mixtures¹⁻⁵. These properties have been used to obtain information about intermolecular interactions and geometrical effects in these systems. The study of these effects in liquid mixtures and in solutions has been of interest in our laboratory in recent years⁶⁻¹⁰. Thus, in the present paper, we have synthesized some derivatives of ethylbenzene-1,3-diol and measured the density, ultrasonic velocity and viscosity of these derivatives in dimethylformamide (DMF) solutions at 308.15 K.

Results and discussion

Various acoustical parameters, such as specific impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (K_s), Rao's molar sound function (R_m), the Van der Waals constant (b), molar compressibility (W), intermolecular free length (L_f), relaxation strength (r), free volume (V_f), relative association (R_A), internal pressure (π), apparent molar volume (ϕ_v), apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k) etc. were calculated, using the experimental data of density, sound velocity and viscosity by standard equations¹⁰. Some of these parameters are given in Table 1. Few parameters were correlated with concentrations and the correlation coefficients along with correlation equations are given in Table 2. From these equations, it is clear that excellent linear correlation between some parameters and concentrations were observed.

Table 1 shows that, in case of SOSR1, SOSR3 and SOSR4, velocity increase whereas for SOSR2, it decreases linearly. Ultrasonic velocity depends on intermolecular free

SOSR1 : 4-{2-Aza-1-methyl-2-(4-nitrophenyl)vinyl}-6-ethylbenzene-1,3-diol.

SOSR2 : 4-{2-Aza-2-(3,4-dimethylphenyl)-1-methylvinyl}-6-ethylbenzene-1,3-diol.

SOSR3 : 4-{2-Aza-1-methyl-2-(3-nitrophenyl)vinyl}-6-ethylbenzene-1,3-diol.

SOSR4 : 4-{2-Aza-1-methyl-2-(3-methylphenyl)vinyl}-6-ethylbenzene-1,3-diol.

^ψA part of this paper was presented in 17th Conference of Chemical Thermodynamics, held at University of Rostock, Rostock, Germany from 28th July to 2nd August, 2002.

Table 1. Variation of acoustical parameters with concentration of four derivatives in DMF at 308 K

Conc. mol dm ⁻³	Velocity U m s ⁻¹	Acoustic impedance Z × 10 ⁻³ kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Adiabatic compress. b TPa ⁻¹	Free length L _f × 10 ¹⁰ m	Relative association R _A	Van der Walls constant b × 10 ⁵ m ³ mol ⁻¹	Free volume V _f × 10 ⁻⁹	Internal pressure π m ³ mol ⁻¹
				SOSR1				
0.00	1432.1	1370.9	509.34	0.4330				
0.02	1433.9	1380.8	505.05	0.4322	1.0055	275.57	0.5261	527.09
0.04	1437.1	1386.8	501.76	0.4308	1.0069	283.58	0.5255	522.17
0.06	1440.1	1391.1	499.16	0.4297	13007	298.97	0.5237	516.99
0.08	1442.4	1394.5	497.16	0.4288	1.0075	301.63	0.5237	512.09
0.10	1446.1	1399.7	494.05	0.4275	1.0078	311.01	0.5173	511.29
				SOSR2				
0.02	1489.7	1439.5	466.31	0.4153	0.9962	286.14	0.4755	585.79
0.04	1482.0	1434.4	470.41	0.4171	0.9996	291.46	0.4901	562.82
0.06	1475.9	1429.9	476.86	0.4186	1.0019	297.34	0.4968	549.66
0.08	1468.1	1423.3	478.56	0.4207	1.0044	302.84	0.5201	519.85
0.10	1463.7	1419.9	481.15	0.4218	1.0060	309.21	0.5412	494.59
				SOSR3				
0.02	1443.2	1390.7	498.36	0.4293	1.0038	277.01	0.4759	583.23
0.04	1447.9	1396.2	497.66	0.4277	1.0036	286.46	0.4809	570.30
0.06	1449.3	1399.9	492.89	0.4270	1.0050	294.97	0.4753	570.73
0.08	1454.3	1408.2	488.29	0.4250	1.0063	304.19	0.4726	568.04
0.10	1459.1	1415.3	484.24	0.4153	1.0070	313.68	0.4728	561.91
				SOSR4				
0.02	1483.3	1436.2	469.39	0.4167	0.9999	283.16	0.4772	585.24
0.04	1486.1	1447.3	464.93	0.4147	1.0051	288.85	0.4676	593.88
0.06	1489.5	1453.0	462.05	0.4134	1.0060	295.92	0.4486	613.82
0.08	1494.9	1461.1	457.82	0.4118	1.0067	303.44	0.4311	633.68
0.10	1498.9	1468.2	454.41	0.4099	1.0080	310.58	0.4206	644.51

Table 2. The correlation coefficients (γ) and correlation equations between some acoustical parameters and concentrations (C) of the four derivatives in DMF solutions at 308 K

Parameters	(γ)	Correlation equation	(γ)	Correlation equation
		SOSR1		SOSR2
U (m s ⁻¹)	0.9980	U + 14850C = 143101	0.9965	U - 32950C = 149565
Z (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.9865	Z + 22750C = 137693	0.9966	Z - 25150C = 144449
K _s (TPa ⁻¹)	0.9970	K _s - 1.3 × 10 ⁻¹¹ C = 5.07 × 10 ⁻¹¹	0.9769	K _s + 1.89 × 10 ⁻¹¹ C = 4.63 × 10 ⁻¹¹
η (Pas)	0.9959	η + 0.0087C = 0.0133	0.9817	η - 0.0269C = 0.0012
r	0.9980	r - 0.1670C = 0.2001	0.8742	r + 0.4855C = 0.11575
W	0.9999	W + 2102.93C = 2245.77W	0.9996	W + 1638.25C = 2267.11
R _m	0.9999	R _m + 3705.43C = 3974.32	0.9999	R _m + 2931.17C = 3881.36
b	0.9819	b + 444.6255C = 267.4740	0.9996	b + 287.5050C = 280.1478
L _f (m)	0.9975	L _f - 0.0570C = 0.4332	0.9967	L _f + 0.0830C = 0.4137
		SOSR3		SOSR4
U (m s ⁻¹)	0.9878	U + 19100C = 143930	0.9933	U + 20100C = 147850
Z (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.9922	Z + 30900C = 138346	0.9951	Z + 38900C = 142982
K _s (TPa ⁻¹)	0.9916	K _s - 1.7 × 10 ⁻¹¹ C = 5.02 × 10 ⁻¹¹	0.9983	K _s - 1.9 × 10 ⁻¹¹ C = 4.73 × 10 ⁻¹¹
η (Pas)	0.9745	η + 0.0156C = 0.0107	0.9948	η + 0.0555C = 0.0099
r	0.9879	r - 0.2165C = 0.1908	0.9931	r - 0.2331C = 0.1462
W	0.9981	W + 2117.86C = 2246.14	0.9986	W + 1472.58C = 2257.36
R _m	0.9999	R _m + 3618.42C = 3986.96	0.9999	R _m + 2553.99C = 3998.20
b	0.9998	b - 455.42C = 322.59	0.9989	b + 347.1830C = 275.5603
L _f (m)	0.9899	L _f - 0.0745C = 0.4309	0.9981	L _f - 0.0819C = 0.4182

length (L_f). With decrease of free length, velocity increases or vice versa. It is observed that L_f decreases for SOSR1, SOSR3 and SOSR4 whereas it increases for SOSR2. Hence, an increase in velocity was observed in SOSR1,

SOSR3 and SOSR4 whereas decrease is observed in SOSR2 system. R_m, W and b increase continuously for all the four systems suggesting thereby absence of complex formation. K_s and r are also observed to decrease for

SOSR1, SOSR3 and SOSR4 systems but increases for SOSR2 system. Decrease in r and L_f and increase of Z , suggest presence of solvent-solute interactions in SOSR1, SOSR3 and SOSR4 whereas for SOSR2 system, r and L_f increases and Z decreases. The increase in r suggests predominance of solute-solute interaction whereas decrease in r is due to solute-solute interactions. This is further confirmed by viscosity values. Viscosity decreases in SOSR2 system and increase in the rest of the three systems, suggesting thereby more association between solute-solvent molecules in latter systems.

Free volume values are observed to increase in SOSR2 system. However, these are observed to decrease in other three systems due to close association between solute and solvent molecules. Thus it is observed that SOSR2 shows different results than those of other three compounds.

Comparison of structures of four compounds shows that in SOSR1 and SOSR3, there is NO_2 group in para and meta positions. In SOSR4 there is one $-\text{CH}_3$ groups in meta position. However, in SOSR2 there are two $-\text{CH}_3$ groups.

From above findings, it is concluded that presence of two methyl groups may causes steric hindrance, which causes breaking of structure, thus causing decrease of viscosity. This is also supported by intermolecular free length, which increases causing ultrasonic velocity and acoustic impedance to decrease and increase of isentropic compressibility. This is further supported by increase in free volume in SOSR2 system.

Experimental

The derivatives of ethylbenzene-1,3-diol were synthesized in our laboratory and purified. The structure of these compounds was confirmed by IR, NMR and CHN analyses.

The solvent dimethylformamide used was of laboratory

grade and was purified prior to use by an appropriate method¹¹. The estimated purity was better than 99.8%.

Solutions of different concentrations were prepared for each compound. The density, ultrasonic velocity and viscosity of pure solvent and of solutions were measured at 308.15 K by using a pycnometer, the single frequency interferometer, operating at 2 MHz and Ubbelohde viscometer with an accuracy of 0.0001 g/ml, $\pm 0.01\%$ and $\pm 0.06\%$, respectively. The accuracy in concentration is ± 0.0001 mol/dm³.

Acknowledgement

Author is thankful to the Head of Chemistry Department for providing facilities.

References

1. B. L. Marwein and S. N. Bhat, *Acustica*, 1985, **58**, 243.
2. N. Indrawati, Mudjijati, F. Wicaksana and H. Hindarso, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2001, **45**, 134.
3. E. Junquera, E. Aicart and G. Tardajo, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 2000, **32**, 1045.
4. Jagan Nath, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1996, **28**, 1083.
5. J. D. Pandey, A. Misra, N. Hasan and K. Misra, *Acoustics Lett.*, 1991, **15**, 105.
6. Shipra Baluja and P. H. Parsania, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1995, **7**, 417.
7. Shipra Baluja and Swati Oza, *Fluid Phase Equilibria*, 2002, **200**, 11.
8. K. M. Rajkotia, Shipra Baluja and P. H. Parsania, *Eur. Polym. J.*, 1997, **33**, 1005.
9. Shipra Baluja and H. S. Joshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 408.
10. Shipra Baluja and Swati Oza, *Fluid Phase Equilibria*, 2001, **178**, 233.
11. J. A. Riddick, W. B. Bunger and T. Sakano, "Organic Solvents - Physical Properties and Methods of Purification", 4th. ed., Techniques of Chemistry, Vol. II, Wiley-Interscience Publication, John Wiley.